

Bayesian inference of phylogeny is robust to substitution model over-parameterization

Supporting Information

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S1 Variable sites in simulated data sets

Figure S1: Histogram of relative number of variable sites in the data sets for each simulation scenario. The data were simulated in RevBayes [5]. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

S2 Credible interval for the Tree Length

Figure S2: The 95% credible interval for the tree length for the inference with Jukes-Cantor [JC, 6] against the inference with GTR+ Γ +I [8, 9, 3] under the **Tame** prior. On the x-axis we show the estimated 95% credible interval size for the JC substitution model (true model). On the y-axis we plot the estimated 95% credible interval for the over-parametrized substitution model. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

Figure S3: The 95% credible interval for the tree length for the inference with Jukes-Cantor [JC, 6] against the inference with GTR+ Γ +I [8, 9, 3] under the MrBayes prior [7]. On the x-axis we show the estimated 95% credible interval size for the JC substitution model (true model). On the y-axis we plot the estimated 95% credible interval for the over-parametrized substitution model. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

Figure S4: The 95% credible interval for the tree length for the inference with Jukes-Cantor [JC, 6] against the inference with GTR+ Γ +I [8, 9, 3] under the RevBayes prior [4]. On the x-axis we show the estimated 95% credible interval size for the JC substitution model (true model). On the y-axis we plot the estimated 95% credible interval for the over-parametrized substitution model. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

Figure S5: The 95% credible interval for the tree length for the inference with Jukes-Cantor [JC, 6] against the inference with GTR+ Γ +I [8, 9, 3] under the BEAST2 prior [1]. On the x-axis we show the estimated 95% credible interval size for the JC substitution model (true model). On the y-axis we plot the estimated 95% credible interval for the over-parametrized substitution model. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

S3 Mean Tree Length for 100 sites and short branch lengths

Figure S6: Comparison of mean tree length between [JC, 6] and GTR+ Γ +I [8, 9, 3] for the data sets with 16 taxa, 100 sites and mean branch length 0.02. The x-axis represents the mean tree length for the inference under JC, while the y-axis represents the mean tree length for the inference under GTR+ Γ +I. Each plot displays the means for the inference with the four different prior schemes.

Figure S7: Comparison of mean tree length between [JC, 6] and GTR+ Γ +I [8, 9, 3] for the data sets with 64 taxa, 100 sites and mean branch length 0.02. The x-axis represents the mean tree length for the inference under JC, while the y-axis represents the mean tree length for the inference under GTR+ Γ +I. Each plot displays the means for the inference with the four different prior schemes.

S4 Further exploration of model combinations

Figure S8: Posterior distributions for tree length for one example of each data set. Each line corresponds to a different model (JC, JC+I, JC+ Γ , JC+ Γ +I, GTR, GTR+I, GTR+ Γ , GTR+ Γ +I; [6, 8, 9, 3]). The GTR models followed the **Tame** prior setting. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

Figure S9: Posterior distributions for tree length for one example of each data set. Each line corresponds to a different model (JC, JC+I, JC+ Γ , JC+ Γ +I, GTR, GTR+I, GTR+ Γ , GTR+ Γ +I; [6, 8, 9, 3]). The GTR models followed the **MrBayes** prior setting. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

Figure S10: Posterior distributions for tree length for one example of each data set. Each line corresponds to a different model (JC, JC+I, JC+ Γ , JC+ Γ +I, GTR, GTR+I, GTR+ Γ , GTR+ Γ +I; [6, 8, 9, 3]). The GTR models followed the **RevBayes** [4] prior setting. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

Figure S11: Posterior distributions for tree length for one example of each data set. Each line corresponds to a different model (JC, JC+I, JC+ Γ , JC+ Γ +I, GTR, GTR+I, GTR+ Γ , GTR+ Γ +I; [6, 8, 9, 3]). The GTR models followed the BEAST2 [1] prior setting. The first row corresponds to the simulated trees with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to the simulated trees with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites.

S5 Simulations with invariable sites

Figure S12: The relationship between posterior probability of bipartitions and the bipartition was correct. The expected behavior is that, on average, the posterior probability and the frequency how often a bipartition with this posterior probability is indeed correct are exactly correlated following the 1:1 line. The trees were simulated with 64 taxa, the mean branch lengths (BL) of 0.1 and 1,000 sites. The data sets were under the JC+ Γ substitution model with $\alpha \in \{0.5, 5, 50\}$. We simulated 1,000 datasets for each α value. We ran inferences under the true model with known and fixed value for α and the over-parameterized substitution model. The over-parameterized model with the **Tame** priors produced statistically consistent estimates of the bipartition posterior probabilities.

Figure S13: Comparison between prior and posterior distributions for the tree length when the data were simulated with among site rate variation (ASVR). We chose **(a)** $\alpha = 0.5$, **(b)** $\alpha = 5$ and **(c)** $\alpha = 50$. In each subfigure, the first row corresponds to a simulated tree with 16 taxa, while the second row corresponds to a simulated tree with 64 taxa. The mean branch lengths (BL) for the data sets are on top of each column. The two first columns display the data sets with 100 sites, the two other columns show the data sets with 1000 sites. The posterior distributions represented correspond to the inference performed under the GTR+ Γ +I model with the 4 different prior settings (Table 2). Note that each prior setting performed equally well when there was indeed ASVR.

S6 Simulations with 256 taxa

Figure S14: The relationship between posterior probability of bipartitions and the bipartition was correct. The expected behavior is that, on average, the posterior probability and the frequency how often a bipartition with this posterior probability is indeed correct are exactly correlated following the 1:1 line. The trees were simulated with 256 taxa the mean branch lengths (BL) of 0.1. The data sets were simulated for 1000 sites under the JC substitution model. We simulated in total 1,000 datasets. The over-parameterized model with the `Tame` priors produced statistically consistent estimates of the bipartition posterior probabilities.

S7 Convergence assessment example

Figure S15: Convergence assessment plots using the package `Convenience` [2] for one example MCMC from Figure 7. The first column shows the plots for the assessment of convergence for the continuous parameters. The second column displays the assessment of the splits in the tree. In all plots the values are within the gray shaded area, which indicates that convergence was achieved.

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